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SPATIAL BAYESIAN MODELLING APPLIED TO THE SURVEYS OF XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA IN ALICANTE (SPAIN)

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The bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa* is characterized by genetic diversity, pathogenic plasticity and wide host range. In North America, risk levels for *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa* were described based on minimum winter temperature. However, it is unknown whether these temperature thresholds can be extrapolated to other bacterial subspecies. Here, the effect of climatic and spatial factors in the distribution of *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* in almond in Alicante was studied. Data were analyzed using a Bayesian spatial hierarchical model in which the spatial component was incorporated via a conditional autoregressive structure (iCAR). Posterior distributions of the model parameters were approximated using the Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation method. Due to the limited study area, the climatic covariates had little variability and they were not very influential in the models compared with the spatial component. Nevertheless, the pathogen was detected within all temperature thresholds, further confirming the climatic adaptability of *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex*.